

Zelenin H.*Educational and Research Institute "Ukrainian Engineering Pedagogics Academy" of V. N. Karazin National University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072333>**ROLE OF MULTILINGUAL COMPETENCE IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE ENGINEERING SPECIALISTS****Зеленін Г.***Навчально-науковий інститут «Українська інженерно-педагогічна академія» Харківського Національного університету імені В. Н. Каразіна***РОЛЬ БАГАТОМОВНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ У ПІДГОТОВЦІ МАЙБУТНІХ ФАХІВЦІВ ІНЖЕНЕРНОГО ПРОФІЛЮ****Анотація**

Стаття присвячена питанням багатомовного навчання у закладах вищої професійної освіти та його впливу на професійну підготовку майбутніх фахівців. Розглянуто основні переваги багатомовної освіти, зокрема підвищення конкурентоспроможності інженерів, доступ до міжнародних наукових даних, розвиток комунікативних навичок і формування академічної мобільності. Аналізуються сучасні методи інтеграції іноземних мов у процес інженерної освіти, включно з паралельним вивченням профільних дисциплін двома мовами, використанням сучасних освітніх технологій та участю студентів у міжнародних програмах. Зроблено висновок про необхідність багатомовної підготовки як важливого елемента сучасної системи інженерної освіти, що сприяє розвитку професійних компетенцій та адаптації фахівців до вимог глобального ринку праці. Автор зазначає, що впровадження інноваційних методик викладання, розвиток партнерських відносин з міжнародними освітніми установами та підвищення кваліфікації викладацького складу є ключовими факторами успішного розвитку багатомовної освіти у вищій професійній школі.

Abstract

The article is devoted to the problems of multilingual education in higher vocational education institutions and its impact on the professional training of future specialists. The main advantages of multilingual education have been considered, in particular, increasing the competitiveness of future engineers, access to international scientific data, development of communication skills and academic mobility. The modern methods of integrating foreign languages into the process of engineering education have been analyzed, including the parallel study of major disciplines in two languages, using modern educational technologies and student engagement in international educational programs. It is concluded that multilingual training is necessary as an important element of the modern system of engineering education, which contributes to the development of professional competencies and adaptation of specialists to the requirements of the global labor market. The author emphasizes that the introduction of innovative teaching methods, the development of partnerships with international educational institutions and the advanced training of teaching staff are key factors in the successful development of multilingual education in higher vocational education.

Ключові слова: багатомовна освіта, вища професійна освіта, професійна підготовка, комунікативні навички, академічна мобільність, іноземні мови, освітні технології, професійні компетенції, розвиток викладацького складу.

Key words: multilingual education, higher vocational education, professional training, communication skills, academic mobility, foreign languages, educational technologies, professional competencies, teaching staff development.

Problem statement. Presently, objective preconditions for the Ukrainian higher engineering education integration into the common educational space of the most developed countries in the world have become reasonable. It provides new opportunities for professional formation of future engineers and development of engineering specialties, as unification and internationalization of engineering education presupposes academic and professional mobility of Ukrainian students and specialists. However, the implementation of the Bologna model in the system of higher Ukrainian engineering education is accompanied by a number of dif-

ficulties, in particular, student mobility (studies in European universities) and specialists' professional mobility are limited mainly by language reasons, i.e. insufficient proficiency in foreign language.

All these factors, to some extent, present corresponding requirements to the quality of foreign language training in the modern Ukrainian higher engineering education. The modern educational paradigm, which is currently being established in engineering education, reflects the modern vision of the relationship between education and culture, where education acts as a universal mechanism for the development of a specialist's personality, free from stereotypes of thinking and acting, capable of intercultural communication and

professional interaction in a foreign-language environment.

At the same time, the existing educational traditions in teaching foreign languages in universities are largely focused on the formation of foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for a specialist to use information from written sources, which is absolutely unacceptable in the actual situation in which intercultural and interethnic contacts become a necessity for every modern engineer.

Literature review. The problem of training in higher engineering education and increasing the efficiency of education has always been topical. Such researchers as I.M. Dichkovskaya, V.I. Kozlov, M.A. Bondarenko focused on pedagogical innovations, studying the introduction of new methods and technologies in the educational process of higher school [1,2,3]. Their works contribute to the understanding of how innovative approaches can improve the quality of specialist training. M.Y. Oleshkov, O.V. Chumak investigate the theoretical foundations of the formation and development of innovative educational systems, offering strategies for modernization of higher education in Ukraine. Their works help to form modern educational models that meet the requirements of the time

Many studies are devoted to the problems of foreign language teaching in higher vocational education (O.V. Ilkova, L.V. Kondrashova, I.I. Vakulik, O.V. Bryntseva, etc.). The researchers have made a significant contribution to the development of the theory and practice of foreign language training in higher vocational institutions in Ukraine, offering various approaches and solutions to improve the effectiveness of training and adapt educational programs to modern requirements. Nevertheless, the problem of preparation for professional bilingual communication of students of engineering specialties in the context of modern requirements to the personality of a technical specialist is currently underdeveloped in pedagogical science and educational practice.

The study aims to analyze and substantiate the necessity of multilingual competence formation in engineering and pedagogical students under the conditions of modern educational process. The article discusses the key contradictions determining the relevance of training future engineers in professional multilingual communication, as well as the main components of multilingual education, its advantages and practical ways of integration into the educational process.

The statement of the main material. In general, the relevance of training bachelors of engineering university for professional bilingual communication is caused by the following contradictions: between the increased requirements of modern society to the personality of a future engineer and the existing shortcomings in the system of their professional and language training; between the theoretical understanding the problem of forming the readiness of future specialists to professional bilingual communication and the actual practice of teaching foreign languages; between the necessity to develop effective pedagogical conditions for the formation of future engineers' readiness for professional bilingual communication and insufficient development of this problem in pedagogical science and educational practice.

The modern level of science and technology development as well as integration processes in European higher engineering education require from engineering graduates the readiness to carry out educational and future professional activities in both native and foreign language environment. In this regard, the training of future engineers for professional bilingual communication is becoming actualized, which is a process of in-depth study of a foreign language by students in the format of professional and intercultural immersion considering the specifics of engineering activity, parallel study of general vocational disciplines in two languages, conducting activities in the reference system of a foreign language.

Multilingual teaching of engineering disciplines allows students not only to master specialized knowledge, but also to adapt to international standards, use foreign scientific publications, and interact with foreign colleagues and partners. Globalization of engineering activity requires high-level linguistic competence from specialists, as modern engineering projects are often implemented in cross-national teams where the working language is English, German, French or another foreign language.

Based on the analysis of scientific and methodological literature, the following main components of multilingual training of bachelors at a engineering university can be identified:

- Advanced study of a foreign language. Future engineers should master a foreign language not only at the communicative level, but also be able to apply it in their professional activities. This implies learning professional terminology, mastering business correspondence, negotiating and preparing technical documentation in a foreign language. For example, organizing engineering debates in a foreign language, where students discuss technical innovations; carrying out course and diploma projects using foreign technical publications, negotiating with native speakers within the framework of training simulations modeling working situations [4].

- Integration of engineering disciplines and foreign language. One of the effective methods of multilingual education is parallel study of general professional disciplines in two languages. For example, lectures can be conducted in a foreign language, and practical classes - in Ukrainian, or vice versa. This contributes to better assimilation of learning content and development of thinking flexibility. For example, the introduction of bilingual courses, "Theory of mechanisms and machines" in Ukrainian and "Automation of technological processes" in English; solving engineering cases using foreign technical terminology, carrying out laboratory work using instructions in a foreign language.

- Professionally-oriented intercultural immersion. Engineering activity is closely related to international cooperation, so students need to understand the cultural specifics of different countries. An important element of preparation is participation in international educational programs, internships, conferences, seminars and projects where the main language of communication is a foreign language. Participation of students in academic exchange programs (e.g. Erasmus+). For example, implementation of international joint projects with

foreign universities; organization of international engineering hackathons, where teams from different countries solve engineering problems [5].

- Using modern technologies in teaching. Modern online platforms, virtual laboratories, webinars, simulation programs and specialized engineering courses in foreign languages allow students to get up-to-date knowledge, interact with foreign teachers and specialists, and apply the acquired knowledge in practice. For example, taking online courses on Coursera, edX or MIT OpenCourseWare platforms on engineering disciplines in English; working with virtual simulations of engineering processes in a foreign language; participating in online conferences and master classes of the world's leading experts.

Based on our own practical experience, the following advantages of multilingual education for future engineering professionals should be emphasized:

1. Competitiveness. Engineers who speak a foreign language have more opportunities for employment in international companies and participation in global projects. Companies operating in the global market are looking for specialists who can effectively interact with partners and clients from different countries. Speaking a foreign language allows an engineer to take up more prestigious positions and participate in international research initiatives [4].

2. Access to international scientific data. Knowledge of a foreign language allows engineers to work with authentic sources of information, scientific publications and technical documentation. Many leading research and technological innovations are published in English, so the ability to analyze and apply this data gives a specialist a significant advantage. Engineers can also participate in international conferences and publish their research papers in top-rated journals.

3. Development of communication skills. The ability to negotiate, participate in international meetings and communicate effectively with colleagues from other countries is an important skill for a modern engineer. In international projects, where teams consist of specialists from different countries, the ability to clearly formulate one's thoughts and discuss technical solutions in a foreign language plays a key role. It also contributes to professional growth and expansion of business contacts.

4. Adaptability and mobility. Multilingual education provides an opportunity to study and work abroad, as well as to participate in international engineering projects. In today's environment, engineers are increasingly faced with the need to travel, relocate and work in multinational teams. The ability to adapt easily to new linguistic and cultural environment helps specialists to settle into a new workplace faster and to perform their professional duties effectively [6].

Conclusion and further research prospects. Multilingual education in higher engineering institutions is a key factor in training competitive specialists capable of working in a globalized labor market. The article shows that foreign language proficiency significantly increases professional mobility of engineers,

their ability to work with international scientific sources, to communicate effectively in a multinational environment and to adapt to international standards of engineering education.

The main advantages of multilingual education include: increasing the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market; expanding their career opportunities in international companies; access to global scientific data and the possibility of integration into the global scientific community; development of communication skills necessary for participation in international projects and negotiations; formation of adaptability and mobility, allowing engineers to successfully work and study abroad.

To realize effective multilingual training, it is suggested: integration of engineering disciplines and foreign language through bilingual courses and practice-oriented classes; advanced study of professional terminology and development of technical communication skills; introduction of distance learning technologies and participation in international educational programs; development of professional-oriented intercultural interaction through academic exchanges and co-projects with foreign universities. Therefore, multilingual training is an indispensable element of modern Ukrainian engineering education, ensuring the compliance of specialists with the world standards and increasing their professional demand.

Further research perspectives include development of effective teaching methods - development and testing of innovative pedagogical technologies aimed at promoting multilingual competence of engineering students; analysis of successful world practices and evaluation of multilingual training effectiveness.

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